

USE OF CODE SWITCHING IN AB-E-HAYAT BY Umera Ahmed: A Stylistic Analysis with Simpson's Model of Narrative Structure

Sumra Peeran¹, Ufaq Binte Jamal², Shagufta Yasmeen³

¹Academics and Operations Manager, Learning Resource Network LRN UK;
Head International Qualification, Zia Uddin University Exam Board

²Senior Lecturer, Department of Social Science, Mohammad Ali Jinnah University (MAJU)

³Senior lecturer, Department of Humanities and Social Sciences, Bahria University, Karachi
sumra.peeran@lrnglobal.org¹ ufaq_jamal@yahoo.com² shagufta.bukc@bahria.edu.pk³

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Corresponding Author: *

Sumra Peeran

Academics and Operations Manager, Learning Resource Network LRN UK; Head International Qualification, Ziauddin University Exam Board

Email:

sumra.peeran@lrnglobal.org

Abstract

This study examines Umera Ahmed's Urdu novel *Aab-e-Hayat*, the sequel to *Peer-e-Kamil*, through a pragma-stylistic lens. The novel continues the spiritual journey of Salar Sikander and Umamah, who aspire to attain an ideal home reminiscent of Eden. Ahmed's stated purpose is to inspire moral and spiritual refinement by depicting characters who uphold unwavering faith and divine principles derived from the Quran and the Sunnah of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH). Symbolically, *Aab-e-Hayat* ("the water of life") signifies eternal devotion to God that transcends mortality. The research investigates how Ahmed employs linguistic and stylistic techniques, particularly code-switching between Urdu and English, to convey emotions, character development, and thematic resonance. Furthermore, it explores how the novel's linguistic texture reflects ideological tensions between Western interest-based banking systems and Islamic interest-free models. Using Simpson's (1993) model of narrative structure, the study applies qualitative textual analysis to dialogues and direct narration to reveal how linguistic choices reinforce the novel's spiritual and ethical vision.

INTRODUCTION

The study aims to conduct a narrative stylistic analysis of a novel by Umera Ahmed “Aab-e-Hayat,” the sequel of ‘Peer e Kamil’, focusing on sociolinguistic codes that contribute to its narrative depth and reader engagement. By investigating the interplay of pragmatics, semantics, and discourse coherence, the study seeks to explore the implicit meanings within the text to influence its rich sociocultural framework that weaves the linguistic tapestry of the novel.

To better understand the theoretical foundations of this study, pragmatic stylistics facilitates the analysis that examines the social and cultural influences on the language and style of the text. Hence, it involves analyzing the stylistic choices and interpreting texts by considering the way language is used to create real-life situations, and then how language is influenced by the context in which it is used. As the discourse in question is primarily among the educated, elite, and influential class, whereas on the other hand, there are uneducated and trivial characters, it becomes significant to consider the socio-cultural context in which the bilingual use of Urdu and English takes place.

Even though, Urdu literary texts have been analyzed from various perspectives; including code switching, which is a typical practice of analysis. The last decade’s close examination, however, identifies that Simpson’s model of narrative style to explore sociolinguistic codes is rarely used to analyze sociolinguistic codes in Urdu literature. The model has immense potential to explore the linguistic grounding of the narrative structure and how it contributes to character development, thematic depth, and the overall stylistic richness of the text (Simpson, 2004).

Realizing the fact, this study is to investigate the role of code-switching as a narrative device in the novel and the author’s intention

behind employing this technique. This exploration could enhance the understanding of the relationship between language, culture, setting, and storytelling in Umera Ahmed’s work, providing a more comprehensive analysis of the stylistic elements in the novel.

Problem Statement

Despite extensive literary and thematic analyses of Umera Ahmed’s works, limited attention has been given to the linguistic and stylistic dimensions that construct meaning within her narratives. Aab-e-Hayat, as a sequel to Peer-e-Kamil, offers a rich interplay of spirituality, ideology, and modern socio-economic discourse, yet its pragma-stylistic and sociolinguistic layers remain underexplored. The novel’s frequent code-switching between Urdu and English, along with its use of linguistic devices, serves not only aesthetic purposes but also conveys complex emotional, cultural, and ideological meanings. However, there is a lack of scholarly inquiry into how these linguistic strategies contribute to character development, thematic resonance, and the ideological conflict between Western interest-based financial systems and Islamic interest-free principles. Therefore, this study seeks to fill this gap by analyzing Aab-e-Hayat through a linguistic stylistic framework, employing Simpson’s model of narrative structure to uncover how Umera Ahmed’s stylistic choices shape the novel’s spiritual and socio-ethical vision.

Research Objectives

To analyze the narrative structure of Aab-e-Hayat through a pragma-stylistic lens using Simpson’s model.

To investigate the use of sociolinguistic codes and linguistic devices in constructing characters, emotions, and themes

To explore how linguistic and stylistic choices reflect the ideological and thematic conflict between Western interest-based and Islamic interest-free financial systems.

Research Questions

How does Umera Ahmed structure Aab-e-Hayat pragma-stylistically in light of Simpson's model of narrative structure?

How are sociolinguistic codes and linguistic devices employed to construct characters, emotions, and thematic depth?

In what ways do linguistic and stylistic choices reflect the ideological conflict between Western interest-based and Islamic interest-free financial systems?

Significance of the Study

Umera Ahmed's Aab-e-Hayat, the sequel to Peer-e-Kamil (PBUH), extends the spiritual journey of Salar Sikandar and Umaimah Hashim while addressing themes of Islamic banking, moral idealism, and social transformation. The novel reflects the tension between faith and modernity through its characters' personal and ideological struggles. This study is significant as it shifts focus from thematic interpretation to linguistic stylistic analysis, examining how Ahmed's use of pragma-stylistic devices and code-switching shapes character development, emotional expression, and ideological meaning. By applying Simpson's (1993) model of narrative structure, the research contributes to Urdu literary studies by linking language, faith, and narrative technique within a contemporary Islamic framework.

Literature Review

Mehboob (2002), suggested that the purpose of introducing English in South Asia was not merely linguistic but "extralinguistic". This can symbolize a change in the power structure. The position of the English

language in Pakistan as an official language is rising due to the emergence of World Englishes. According to Manan and Gu (2024) World Englishes has established itself as a field of research, exploring indigenous varieties of English from around the world e.g. India, Sri Lanka, Pakistan, Hong Kong, Singapore, Nigeria" that nurtures bilingualism and multilingualism into these societies.

Subsequently, bilingualism is an irrefutable reality on account of post colonialism often manifested through code switching as an innate and innovative process among bilinguals to bridge gaps between languages (Swann & Sinka, 2020). Pakistan, an ethnolinguistically rich country, is highly influenced by the colonial legacy of English as a dominant and official language, leading to the emergence of bilingualism and deficit ideologies (Syed, 2024). Still bilingualism emphasizes the impact of social factors like culture, prestige, religion, and affiliation on language choice and the borrowing of words between languages in the form of code switching and code mixing (Zaman, Chandio, & Wazeer, 2025).

According to a case study conducted by Mallah and Memon (2021), Pakistan has several vernaculars along with 5 major languages; Urdu, Punjabi, Sindhi, Balochi, and Pashto, in public or private schools, still English is the medium of instruction in most schools, although it is not a mother tongue of any region in Pakistan. English in Pakistan functioned as a 'superstrate' language due to its historical imposition and its continued dominance over indigenous languages (Ullah & Akram, 2023). Therefore, the English language has gradually penetrated in the Pakistani society.

Therefore, cultural identity of any society is revealed through its language, religion, and customs (Nanda, 2021), likewise the diversity of its linguistic landscape is depicted through

code switching and code mixing. Code switching and code mixing serve to emphasize, express emotion, or connect with specific groups (Zaman, Wasim, & Chandio, 2025). Hence, these techniques highlight cultural hybridity, reflecting Pakistan's complex history and societal fabric.

Since, the prevalence of code-switching in Pakistani literature is linked with the country's multilingual and multicultural landscape, where it provides insights into the sociolinguistic dynamics and the changing patterns of language use in the country; the application of Simpson's Model helps to analyze how the author's linguistic choices contribute to the development and portrayal of the novel's characters, their motivations, and their relationships.

Moreover, the study also identifies different types of code-switching, such as intra-sentential switching (switching within a sentence) and insertion (incorporating English words or phrases into Urdu text) Intra-sentential switching is found to be the most common type of code-switching in Pakistani English literature. Furthermore, the use of code-switching is seen to reflect the linguistic reality of Pakistani society, where the blending of English with other languages like, Urdu, Sindhi, Punjabi, Saraiki, Pashto and Baluchi etc. is a reality.

Theoretical Framework

The study is grounded in Simpson's model of narrative structure, which examines various components of storytelling (Simpson, 2004). This includes analyzing the narrative organization and presentation, the underlying ideologies and social norms that influence themes and characters, the textual functions and literary techniques used to impact readers, as well as the development of characters, their motivations, relationships, and roles in advancing the plot. This comprehensive

framework provides a robust theoretical foundation for the stylistic analysis of the novel.

Later this leads to focus on the thematic content of the narrative, including the central conflicts, events, and resolutions depicted within the story. Finally, this model emphasizes the importance of sociocultural context including historical background, cultural norms, and societal values that may influence the creation and interpretation of the narrative. Hence, the Simpson model provides a comprehensive framework for analyzing the structure, content, and ideological underpinnings of narratives, offering insights into how stories are constructed and obtain their broader cultural significance.

The Components of Simpson’s Model of Narrative Structure 2004

It is utilized here to identify the author’s choice of techniques used in ‘represented storyline’ from the six major domains in stylistics. One of them is the analysis of sociolinguistic codes, which means to explore code-switching and code mixing through idiolect, sociolect, dialect, and registers used in the novel. Because, when stylistic choices are aligned with social identities using sociolinguistic codes, they become more real and relatable. Therefore, the author “may intentionally use specific linguistic features to convey characters’ backgrounds, social status, Or cultural affiliations” (Murtaza & Qasmi, 2013)

Likewise sociolinguistic codes refer to the various linguistic varieties influenced by the social and cultural context of a text. Simpson proposed that this is a crucial tool for organizing not only narrative but all forms of literary discourse. In monolingual English writing, this code is typically limited to the parameters of a single language and its subvarieties. However, in bilingual writing, it is common for multiple indigenous language varieties to mix, often alongside a dominant language such as English (Sah & Li, 2024). In this novel, also the use of bilingual code-switching has emphasized the postcolonial history that depicts the proficiency in two languages that can further incorporates indigenous languages into it.

Ahmed choice of code switching has aligned the social identities of bilinguals with the context and complexity of the relationships among the characters. Harya (2018) in *Sociolinguistics Code: Code Switching and Code Mixing*, quoted Arifin (2011) to mention three contextual factors that should be considered; the relationship amongst speakers, the setting where the talk takes place, and the topic being discussed.

Particularly, code-switching in Pakistani novels serves various functions, such as representing cultural elements, addressing modes of communication, and appealing to a bilingual readership for this reason, there is a need to explore the narrative pragma stylistically, focusing on how language is used.

The Simpsons’ model of narrative structure 2004

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative research approach, employing textual analysis to examine Umera Ahmed’s *Aab-e-Hayat* through Simpson’s (2004) model of narrative structure. The model’s three components— narrative mode, point of view, and modality, serve as the analytical framework for exploring the author’s stylistic choices in constructing plot, characterization, and thematic depth.

The analysis focuses on sociolinguistic codes, particularly code-switching and code-mixing, to understand their functions in conveying identity, emotion, and ideological meaning. Using purposive sampling, relevant excerpts from the 700-page novel were non-randomly selected to illustrate key examples of intrasentential and intersentential code-switching.

The study integrates stylistic and thematic analyses to reveal how linguistic and narrative techniques represent power relations, social hierarchies, and moral ideals. This combined approach enables a deeper understanding of how Ahmed's pragma-stylistic strategies reinforce the novel's spiritual, social, and ideological dimensions.

Findings and Discussions

In Aab-e-Hayat, the narrative structure is tightly woven, making it challenging to individually identify the various elements like narrative, ideologies, textual functions, characters, themes, and sociocultural context. These components are primarily overlapping, and the functionality of code-switching is multidimensional, serving various aspects of the narrative model simultaneously.

Code-switching in the novel serves to build social identities, reveal power dynamics of the elite class, and achieve communicative goals among professionals and laymen. The author's pragmatic considerations influence the choice and execution of code-switching.

While narrating multiple events, the author also utilizes code-mixing for several reasons. She uses English lexemes at the phrasal level due to the readers' familiarity with those terms in a bilingual context, or because those lexemes are commonly referred to in English, and Urdu alternatives are either nonexistent or not widely used among the general population. For instance, the highlighted words in different contexts portray the protagonist's elite personality and the society he belongs to.

She also intended to compare the past and present of Salar, so she skillfully weaves together Salar's and Umaima's characters, reflecting their shared context and interactions. The author uses code-switching to create a more realistic and comprehensive portrayal of their lives. This technique not

only enhances character development but also makes the narrative more natural and engaging.

Textual reference 1: Vo koray daan ka dhakan hataye, (pg 37)

(Please see the appendix)

Here the author uses the Urdu lexeme 'Koray daan' which is rarely used in communication hence later she refers the same with waste basket as a common term use in real life. These lines also give comparison of two extreme phases of Salar's life the former irreligious pervert Salar and now a firm and practicing Muslim.

The author also refers to Salar's social class by indicating his everyday activities and routine life. Also, giving an indication about his temperament, attitude, and behavior with the people he works with and interacting with on daily basis.

Textual reference 2: 'Vo 1st class se suffer kar rahay thay(pg 82)

(please see the appendix)

The passengers who travel in an airplane's first class typically belong to the elite class of society, including politicians, bureaucrats, businessmen, and celebrities. The high airfare for first class makes it unaffordable for the middle class. Given their elite and educated status, these passengers predominantly use English language, possibly due to a lack of common alternatives. However, the author could have used the word "musafir" (traveler) instead of "passenger," which is an Urdu lexeme. The choice of language may also relate to the author's academic background in English.

While skillfully portraying character's linguistic personality, the author has utilized English lexical items because Urdu language lacks the alternatives. For example, bank, boardroom, presentation, and team. However, the equivalents of highlighted words in English language are available in Advance

Urdu but less common or lacks the acuity of the word, for example the word "credibility" has the equivalent "Mu'tabiriyet," while the Urdu words for "trust factor" include "T'timad" (trust), "Bharosa" (belief/confidence), and "T'tibar".

Even though, 'Mutabiriyet' is exact literal alternative, yet it is an uncommon word as compare to itibar still the author chooses not to write those Urdu words in her novel and its not because she intend to demean the language otherwise she would chose English language to write this novel, but her intentions are as she told in the preface to create realistic and ideal characters that we can feel them alive.

The author once again exhibits Salar's demanding career that initially compromises his new marital life. The day after his wedding, instead of taking time off, he's at the office, fully immersed in an audit presentation to establish its credibility and trustworthiness. Meanwhile, his newlywed wife is upset and complaining to their mentor, tarnishing her husband's image.

Textual reference 3: 'Wahan se das meel k faslay per apnay bank k boardroom....(pg 20) (please see the appendix)

The author employs code switching deliberately to underscore the contrast between two pivotal aspects of Salar's life: his unwavering professional commitment on one end and the nascent state of his marital relationship on the other.

In contrast to the reference, the author also portrays Salar's grandeur by depicting his immense love through an opulent and exquisite gift for his wife—a dream for anyone in their elite social class. Simultaneously, Umaima's naivety shines through as she remains blissfully unaware of wearing the most expensive piece of jewelry. Ahmed strategically weaves such events to vividly depict the elite class, emphasizing

their boundless wealth, leisurely pursuits, and extravagant choices. However, true to Ahmed's style of creating dual meanings, this narrative subtly outwits the readers.

Textual reference 4: Oh! Tiffany statement."....(pg 177)

(please see the appendix)

Ahmed skillfully employs code switching in this scene, deftly weaving in elements such as the brand name "Tiffany," the exotic-sounding supporting character Mrs. Zaviyars, and inter-sentential code switching with translations in both Urdu and English.

Through this event, Ahmed vividly portrays the sociocultural context and highlights Salar's persona as an ideal husband with refined taste.

On the other hand, developing a contrast from his ingenuity to his naivety in understanding a sensitive and demanding Umaima, Ahmed use lots of English lexemes and phrasal verbs that are having no alternatives and must be in Salar's style of language

Textual reference 5: Wo is ghair mulki bank (pg 58)

(please see the appendix)

To illustrate corporate sector, nouns from register contributes to the theme of the novel that is transition from abandoning a well-made career in western banking system at its peak to developing Islamic financial system from scratch. Additionally, this is Salaar's realization of his failure as a husband to comprehend Umaima's traumas and challenges resonates with the experiences of many women worldwide. It serves as a poignant reminder of men's struggle to truly understand women.

The discourse between protagonists reflects the significance of accepting other's values and giving space in marital life, which is a relevant phenomenon today. To fabricate the dilemma, Ahmed's use of code-switching

makes it not only natural but effectively enhances the narrative.

Moreover, Ahmed has provided the translation in English and Urdu to make the discourse comprehensive in the bilingual code. For instance, violation is referred to as *Khilaf warzi*, *mokef* referred as *stance*. Here the interesting point is the translation of a word in English to Urdu and then immediately Urdu to English, which gives an definite impression that her writing is inclusive and she values her readers linguistic competence, which means she wants everyone to understand her meanings.

Textual reference 6: *Tum tu Hafiz e Quran ho ...* (Pg 259)

(please see the appendix)

The above lines show the apprehension of Umaima, she was against Salar's decision to keep working in the World Bank and procrastinate his dream to establish an interest-free economic system. She firmly tells him that you are 40 and if not, now then never will he do anything to pursue his dream, which is a much needed and expected thing from him. The use of strong vocabulary like violation shows her utter desire while pushing him hard to initiate Islamic banking system.

The war against societal norms, conventions, and corrupt systems is challenging for both Salar Sikander and Ahmed as protagonist and narrator, respectively. The author uses these contests to expose the vices of the Western world and employs code switching to engage a diverse readership. Examples include using terms like "world bank," "charter," "project," and "NGOs" to create a sense of familiarity and understanding. Additionally, the author uses vivid imagery with strong words like "grenade" to create a powerful impact.

Textual reference 7: *World bank k charter ki*(Pg 294)

(please see the appendix)

Salaar's official situation is highlighted through code switching, including intra-sentential (using different languages within a sentence) and inter-sentential (using different languages between sentences) techniques. This adds depth to the narrative and reflects the complexities of Salaar's situation.

Textual reference 8: *Tum naraz ho mujhe se?....*(Pg 294)

(please see the appendix)

The common perception in Pakistan is that code-switching is limited to the English language. However, code-switching involves using multiple languages within a speech event. As Pakistan is a multilingual country, it is inaccurate and illogical to consider it a strictly bilingual state. Writers aiming to portray realistic characters cannot avoid using other indigenous languages in their work.

In the novel, when Umaima experiences the sudden deaths of her brothers, she becomes severely depressed and leaves her home. While walking, she encounters an old woman carrying a heavy load of dried twigs. Umaima helps the woman carry her load to her mud hut, symbolically offloading her own emotional burden. In the hut, the old woman shares profound and spiritual insights that ultimately restore hope for Umaima.

Textual reference 9: *Jo Vichora Allah ...* (pg. 276)

(please see the appendix)

In the narrative, there is intrasentential code switching between Punjabi and Urdu. The term "vichora" is a pure Punjabi word meaning "taking apart" or separation, but it is sometimes used in Saraiki. This example illustrates *mise en abyme*, where the author introduces an external character and its story to create a recursive effect. The old lady has chosen to live alone and raise her 38-year-old disabled and mentally challenged son. This parallels Umaima's choice to live alone and carry her depression, bringing the narrative

closer to the lived experiences of people in the outskirts of Lahore, Punjab. The author weaves this sociocultural context using vivid imagery and code switching between Urdu and Punjabi, the languages of the local population.

Not only the narratives around Salar and Umaima are bilingual, but even their children's conversations are full of code-switching, particularly highlighting the influence of living abroad, the high-class education, and above all being extremely brilliant, which they inherit from their father. For instance, to build Salaar's eldest son Jabril's character the author writes.

Textual reference 10: Tera saal ki umer mein.... (Pg 553)

(Please see the appendix)

The study explores code-switching in children's conversations, highlighting their academic intelligence and nurturing attitudes, particularly Jabril. The use of English words without Urdu translations suggests convenience. The study also identifies inter-sentential code-switching, such as in a conversation about the Spelling bee contest. The conversation between Anaya and Raisa shows how caring the children are to each other and how supportive they are.

Textual reference 11: There is always a next time...(pg-558).

(Please see the appendix)

So, the novel has numerous instances where the children, including Jabril, Hameen, Anaya, and Raisa, demonstrate support and care for one another, as well as for their parents. This reflects the strong upbringing and nurturing environment they have experienced.

Conclusion

Hence, the story is about Salar and Umaimah's achievements of their big goals both as individuals and as couple in their

personal and social lives along with lots of ups and downs while staying together firm and grounded. They perform well to fulfill their religious and moral duties while facing lots of hardships as shown in the novel.

It was a journey not only for the characters but for the author who takes her reader along with her in this journey from start till end and succeeds in not leaving the readers alone at any point of time. Everything seems so real and natural and this all happens due to the choice of code switching in a particular narrative style with the help of deep understanding of sociolinguistic context of the novel.

In this study close scrutiny of references taken from the original text has shown a few number of code switching instances between Urdu and English languages, and at one even between Urdu and Punjabi. The meticulous examination through vigilant textual analysis reveals the inexorable use of code switching, without which to demonstrate and enhance authenticity and relatability becomes challenging. Through the vivid characters and real-life situations particular actual language that one can feel hearing in everyday life makes this novel an exceptional and easy to gain acceptance and popularity.

Since the entire novel is full of code-switching by many characters for multiple reasons, this study further extends the research on finding more and more reasons for code-switching to safely suggest that this deliberate code-switching is not only the influence of sociocultural tapestry, but it is the need of the narrative structure, because so far, many terms do not have their exact translations in Urdu and if they have then its either in advance Urdu or they are not very common and comprehensive. Therefore, it becomes unavoidable and mandatory to identify the social class and intelligence of Salaar Sikander and his clan, with the use of

the most acceptable linguistic device that is codeswitching in the Urdu and English languages within this context.

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